

Leveraging Federated Search and Data Annotation for Enhanced Analysis of Biography Networks and Network Biographies

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Introduction

The proliferation of knowledge graphs has advanced the representation and interlinking of data across diverse fields, enhancing semantic integration and data retrieval. In the digital humanities, Linked Open Data (LOD) principles are applied to construct complex graphs, often featuring biographical networks; numerous examples can be found on the DaSCH platform [1] and explored through its web application [2]. Increasingly, such networks are being integrated into the broader web of data, as projects interconnect related information across heterogeneous repositories. While these networks facilitate discovery, they often require users to access multiple platforms. Federated search technology addresses this challenge by providing a unified interface for querying multiple RDF repositories simultaneously, integrating distributed sources while preserving their autonomy. Through a single interface, users can search across independent databases and view combined results [3]. This approach enables comprehensive analyses of biographical networks by presenting relevant data and linkages on one platform.

Furthermore, for biographical network studies that examine a network's evolution, it is essential to access not only network-level metadata but also metadata about each statement. Recent technologies, such as RDF-star (RDF*), enable this by linking metadata directly to the edges of a knowledge graph and supporting combined querying of data and metadata through SPARQL-star (SPARQL*) [4].

In this paper, I will first demonstrate how federated search can construct a comprehensive biographical network without centralizing data silos by retrieving information from diverse LOD repositories. I will then show how an RDF-based network can be extended with metadata required for biographical analysis using RDF* technology. Both arguments are illustrated with examples from the digital edition of a historical travel diary.

Constructing a Federated Biography Network

The digital edition of Jacob I. Bernoulli's (1654–1705) travel diary, *Reisbüchlein*, on the Bernoulli-Euler Online (BEOL) platform [5], is a notable LOD-based project that employs a federated data retrieval infrastructure. For this edition, the *textToRDFGraph* pipeline [6] is used to generate a knowledge graph by extracting information from the German transcriptions. The pipeline leverages Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, such as named entity recognition (NER), part-of-speech (POS) tagging, and dependency parsing, to identify persons, locations, and the relationships between them. The resulting graph captures a biographical

network of individuals mentioned in the text, detailing their stated relationships and travel activities, and is queryable irrespective of the language of the text [7].

The *textToRDFGraph* pipeline retrieves additional data from open repositories such as Wikidata and DBpedia to enrich and validate the network, linking local resources to their external representations via IRIs. This enables the BEOL web application to access more information about named entities from these external repositories and present it to users through federated searches. Figure 1 illustrates how the web application utilizes federated search to retrieve *Reisbüchlein*'s transcriptions, including embedded named entities from one triplestore (Fuseki), as well as journey details and information about persons and locations from another triplestore (GraphDB), and coordinates of locations and biographical data of persons from Wikidata. All this information is integrated within the web application to provide comprehensive information about individuals and locations, and to generate dynamic journey visualizations on maps. Through this infrastructure, users can access the full content of the *Reisbüchlein*, including its biographical network and all related materials.

Figure 1: Resibüchlein edition's federated search workflow

This federated infrastructure provides users with access to a comprehensive, decentralized biographical network. The web application presenting this infrastructure only needs to ensure the accuracy of the federated queries, without maintaining the third-party data itself. Through this approach, users gain access to the most up-to-date information residing in various repositories and can clearly see the connections across them. At the same time, the owners of the third-party repositories retain complete control over their data and its maintenance.

RDF* for Network Biography

Studying the biography of a data network requires access not only to the data itself but also to the metadata and functionalities that enable such analysis. Using LOD principles, a knowledge graph

can be extended with metadata about the entire dataset by assigning a name to the graph [8]. Named graphs are typically employed for data management, access control, or attaching metadata to the graph as a whole. However, examining the network's biography requires analyzing metadata for each unit of knowledge within the dataset.

Scholars require access to metadata about the network edges, including the source of information, the degree of certainty regarding data accuracy, permission rights for specific information, versioning, and creation history. While annotating data with metadata is possible using standard RDF through reification, this process is cumbersome and introduces processing overhead in SPARQL queries [9]. RDF* technology enables metadata to be added directly to each RDF statement (i.e., each edge in the graph), allowing for more efficient querying using SPARQL-star (SPARQL*) [10].

The *Reisbüchlein* edition employs RDF* technology not only to represent metadata about the journeys but also to capture metadata essential for the biographical study of the dataset itself. For this purpose, the RDF-star-based ontology *JourneyStar* [11], using the prefix `js`, is employed. It provides constructs (classes and predicates) to represent travel data along with all associated metadata comprehensively. This ontology includes a variety of metadata constructs.

For example, using the predicate `js:mentionedIn`, the source document from which data is extracted can be linked to the corresponding edge in the graph. The source may be an internal resource or an external one referenced via its IRI. Figure 2 illustrates some of the metadata added to the *Reisbüchlein*. The date when a fact is added to the graph as an RDF triple can be recorded on the edge using `js:creationDate` with an RDF range of `xsd:dateTime`. To ensure precise representation, the date statement can also specify the calendar type through `js:hasCalendar` [12]. In this way, multiple levels of nested metadata can be incorporated into the knowledge graph, supporting detailed biographical studies of the network.

As shown in Figure 2, additional metadata can be added to the graph to enforce permission control using the `js:viewPermission` property, which specifies the types of users allowed to retrieve particular graph statements in read mode. Similarly, other properties can grant edit permissions to specific users, enabling them to modify edges or nodes in the graph. At the same time, creation and deletion rights can be assigned to data owners. Using RDF*, it is therefore possible to incorporate permission control attributes at varying levels of granularity. This approach also facilitates and speeds the verification of access permissions during data retrieval.

Furthermore, the degree of certainty regarding the accuracy of each fact in the graph can be recorded for every RDF statement representing that fact. For example, on page 13, Jacob Bernoulli mentions that he traveled with “H. Frey.” The collaborating editor of the *Reisbüchlein* project was 85% confident that this “Mr. Frey” was Johann Ulrich Frey. As illustrated in Figure

2, the graph includes an edge indicating that `:JohannFrey` participated in the first stage, `:Stage1`, of Bernoulli's first journey, `:Journey1`. The fact that this information was contributed to the knowledge graph by `:EditorA` is captured as metadata via the `js:accordingTo` predicate. Additionally, the editor's uncertainty regarding this fact can be represented in the graph using the `js:certaintyPercentage` predicate.

Figure 2: Example of metadata representation (in green) using RDF*

To ensure data consistency, SHACL shapes can be defined for ontological constructs that specify constraints on the graph's nodes and edges [13]. The *JourneyStar* ontology provides SHACL shapes for all its constructs, enabling validation of both primary data and metadata to ensure conformity of the data graph with the ontology. Stored in the repository, these shapes can also verify future data additions. Triplestores, such as GraphDB, support SHACL validation by generating a validation graph from the rules and matching it with the data graph.

RDF* graphs can likewise be stored in triplestores that provide SPARQL* query endpoints, such as GraphDB. Users can then analyze both data and metadata; for example, filtering data by certainty above 75%, creation date, temporal changes, or source information.

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